
Comparative Analysis of Academic Performance Between Regular NCE and NCE Sandwich Programme in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel, Jigawa State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study is a comparative analysis of academic performance between Regular NCE and NCE Sandwich Programme in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel, Jigawa State, Nigeria. Two research questions were answered and two null hypotheses were tested. The study used ex-post facto research design and the total population used was 1,079 NCE III regular and NCE IV part-time Arabic, Early Childhood care, and Primary Education students in Jigawa State Colleges of Education Gumel from 2022 to 2023 academic sessions. The instrument used for data collection was record of students' Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) and their files to get records of students from office of the Head of Department. The research questions were answered using Mean and standard deviation while chi-square was used to test all the stated null hypotheses. The analysis revealed that the regular students perform better than the part-time students. Findings also revealed that individual differences in terms gender of the part-time and regular students are revealed in favor of Regular Students in their academic achievements. The study concluded that regular program perform better than the part-time program in Jigawa State colleges of Education Gumel. It further concluded that the Female Students perform better than male Students in both Regular and Part time Program. The researcher made some recommendations among which include that lecturers in the colleges of education especially those teaching the part-time students to use appropriate teaching methods that will favour the students in part-time program to help them cope with learning situations. The study further recommended that extra-classes in the form of tutorials should be organized for the part-time classes so as to be able to meet up with the course content of the programme for effective teaching and learning process.

Keyword: Comparative, Analysis, Academic, Performance, NCE Regular, and NCE Sandwich.

Introduction

Education is the root of development of any nation in the world. It is a critical element of human development and an essential ingredient for fulfilling other aspects of human rights such as effective economic, political participation and quality health care delivery. Education is seen as the process of socialization and means by which one acquires knowledge, information and skills in order to live a useful life and contribute meaningfully to the development on one's society. Education is also a veritable instrument for influencing positive change behaviour of citizens educating for national sustainable development. FRN (2014) emphasized the goals of education in Nigeria to include inculcation of the right type of values, attitudes, communication skills as well as life-long skills.

However, in this era of globalization and technological revolution, education is considered as a first step for every human activity. It plays a vital role in the development of human capital and is linked with an individual's well-being and opportunities for better living (Battle & Michael 2020). Education ensures the acquisition of knowledge and skills that enable individuals to increase their productivity and improve their quality of life. This increase in productivity also leads towards new sources of earning which enhances the economic growth of a country (Saxton, 2021). The quality of students' performance remains at top priority for educators. It is meant for making a difference locally, regionally, nationally and globally. Educators, trainers, and researchers have long been interested in exploring factors contributing to quality of performance of learners. Factors, which are inside and outside the school; these factors may be termed as student factors, family factors, school factors, gender and peer group factors (Crosnoe, Johnson & Elder, 2020).

Therefore, At the college of education level, which constitutes the primary focus of this study, Primary Education studies, Early Child Education, and Arabic double Major are the three year full time and four years part-time. Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) programme offered to senior school certificate holders with five "O" Level credit passes. These are reflected in subjects like English Language, Mathematics and any other related subjects for both full time and part-time students. The full-time programme has six (6) semesters in all for the three academic sessions and eight semesters for the part-time programme for four academic sessions. Both programmes have nine (9) months of practical training / orientation i.e. (3 months of Supervised Industrial Work Experienced Scheme and 6 months of Teaching Practice).

Then, Academic performance refers to what students achieve in their studies and how they cope with or accomplish different learning experiences given to them by their teachers. This can be affected sometimes by either age of the students, gender, learning environment or class size. Ibrahim (2019) reported that in education institutions, success is measured by academic achievement or how well a student meets the standard set out by the institutions which is measured through marks, scores or grades.

Age is a determinant factor on students' academic achievement. La Paro and Pianta (2022) presented evidence that older children fare better academically than their younger age appropriate peers. In another study conducted by Uphoff and Gilmore (2015) about the relationship between age and achievement argue that the older and/or more mature student in a class fare better than younger classmate. There were many research works on influence of age maturity on students' academic performance whose findings revealed that, young-age

students are found to be more resistant to academic pressures and perform better than the old-age students. Being this research on regular and part-time students, the researcher observed that, age of the students may have significant impact on students' performance. Age of the individual, as it increases usually affects the various developmental changes and subsequently affects every area of human performance.

Hence, Gender is the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristic pertaining to and differentiating between the feminine and masculine (female and male) population. According to Rao, S.(208) The importance of examining performance in relation to gender is based primarily on the socio-cultural differences between girls and boys. Some vocations and professions have been regarded as men's (Engineering, arts and craft, agriculture etc) while others as women's (catering, typing, nursing etc). Infact chores that are regarded as complex and difficult tasks are allocated to boys whereas girls are expected to handle the relatively easy and less demanding task. As a result of this way of thinking, the larger society has tended to see girls as a weaker sex. Consequently, average Nigerian girl goes to school with these fixed stereotypes. In view of the belief that student gender may have influence on the students' academic performance this study will seek to find the relationship between them if any.

Ndlovu and Moyo (2013) conducted a study on the factors Affecting Performance of Adults in Adult and Continuing Education in Zimbabwe Open University. The purpose of this study was to determine the correlation of the factors affecting academic performance with the performance levels of adults in adult and continuing education in Nkulumane-Emganwini area. The research findings indicate that attendance and academic self-concept have a strong positive correlation with performance. Learning styles and Age were also found to affect performance while marital status and income did not significantly affect performance.

In view of the above, all the described variables constitute the background in which this study was conducted on comparative Analysis of academic achievement between regular NCE and NCE sandwich Programme in colleges of education Gumel Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

A growing number of students are abating for the NCE sandwich due to flexible schedule, but concerns exist regarding its impact on academic performance compared to the regular NCE programme. The high demand for these programmes has necessitated the need for colleges of education in Nigeria especially state colleges in North-west zone Nigeria to offer a place into Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) fulltime and part-time three (3) years and four (4) years respectively. In spite of the over whelming importance and the high demand of these programmers the performance of part-time NCE education students declined compared to regular NCE education students in Jigawa state college of education Gumel.

Despite the increase in enrolment, the performance of the part-time students has not yet improved. The researcher observed that each time results are presented for school considerations and at the academic board for approval, performance of part-time students is usually very poor. Questions are raised and results are frowned at as to why part-time students' results are poor compared to the regular ones. It is on these bases that the researcher collected results of Jigawa State College of Education Gumel for 2022/2023 academic session and observed a decline in the performance comparing the results of the part-time and regular NCE students.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

- i. Determine the overall academic performance between students in NCE Sandwich and NCE Regular Programme in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel
- ii. Identify the mean difference of academic performance between male and female students of Regular NCE and NCE Part time Programme in Jigawa state College of Education Gumel.

Research Question

- i. What is the overall academic performance between students in NCE Sandwich and NCE Regular Programme in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel?
- ii. What is the mean difference of academic performance between male and female students of Regular NCE and NCE Part time Programme in Jigawa state College of Education Gumel?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the significant level of 0.05.

- HO₁: There is no significant difference in the overall academic performance between students in NCE Sandwich and NCE Regular Programme in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel.
- HO₂: There is no significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students of Regular NCE and NCE Part time Programme in Jigawa state College of Education Gumel.

Research Design

This study adopted Ex-post facto research design. According to Akuezuilo and Agu (2024), Ex-post facto design seeks to find out the factors or conditions associated with certain occurrence of past events or of already existing conditions. The choice of this design stems from the fact that already moderated final year results was analyzed in three Departments in Jigawa state Colleges of Education Gumel.

Population of the Study

The population of the study is made up of all the final year students of both the regular and part-time of Arabic, Early childhood care, and primary education, which is made up of NCE III regular and NCE IV part-time Sandwich students of the Jigawa state colleges of education Gumel, 2022/2023 academic session. Accordingly, the population for the study is (1,079) of Arabic double major, Early Childhood Care, and Primary Education students in the state colleges as shown in the Table 1.

Table I: Population of the study

Programme	No of Regular NCE Student	No of Part-time NCE Students	Total
PED	277	148	425
ECCE	380	44	424
ARB/DM	116	114	230
Total	773	306	1,079

Source: Office of the Heads of Department, Arabic, Early childhood care, and Primary Education 2022/2023 Academic Session

Sample Size

The researcher used the total population of the study, the reason of being that the total population of the study is few and manageable for the researcher to analyze. Therefore, there was no need for sample size and sampling technique as shown in table 1.

Instrumentation

In order to collect data for the study, the researcher made used of students' second semester result for 2022/2023 academic session for both regular and part-time students. Since the researcher compared academic achievement of part-time and regular students.

All the data meant to give answers to the research questions were coded into statistical analysis. The data obtained by the researcher from the field were tested statistically using the Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS). Mean and standard deviation were used to answer all the research questions, while chi-square was used to test all the stated null hypotheses. This is because the researcher compared the difference between the performance of part-time and regular students of Arabic, Early Childhood care and Primary Education students in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel.

Results

Research Question One: What is the overall academic performance between students in NCE Sandwich and NCE Regular Programme in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel?

Table 2: The overall academic performance of NCE Sandwich and NCE Regular program in Jigawa State Education Gumel.

Programme	Regular NCE		Part time NCE		of
	No of Students Register	% of Graduating Students	No of Students Register	Percentage Graduating Students	
PED	227	27.7%	148	14.8%	
ECCE	380	38%	44	4.4%	
ARB/DM	116	11.4%	114	11.4%	
Total	773	77.3%	306	30.6%	

Source: Jigawa State College of Education Gumel.

Table 2 shows the overall academic performance between NCE Sandwich and NCE Regular program, this reveals that total percentage of graduating students in Regular NCE is 77.3% (comprising PED, ECCE and ARB/DM) which shows that graduating students are far above the non-graduating students in the NCE Regular program. While in the part time NCE program, it shows that the graduating students in the program are just 30.6% which indicates

that the graduating students are less than the non-graduating students in the Part time NCE program.

Research Question Two: What is the mean difference of academic performance between male and female students of Regular NCE and NCE Part time Programme in Jigawa state College of Education Gumel?

Table 3: Mean difference of the academic performance between male and female students of regular NCE and Part time program in Jigawa State College of Education.

Gender	Regular NCE		Part time NCE			
	N	Mean percentage	Mean difference	N	Mean percentage	Mean difference
Male	349	34.9	7.5	137	13.7	3.2
Female	424	42.4		169	16.9	

Table 3 shows the mean difference of the percentage in the academic performance between male and female students of regular NCE and part time Program in Jigawa State College of Education, for the regular NCE it shows that the mean difference between the male and female graduating students is 7.5 in favour of female students which shows that female graduating students is 42.4% and male graduating student is 34.9%. The mean difference in the percentage of graduating students is 3.2 in favour of the female students, where male graduating students is 13.7% and female graduating students is 16.9%. This result shows that the programme both part time and regular graduates is in favor of female students than male student.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the overall academic performance between students in NCE Sandwich and NCE Regular Programme in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel.

Table 4: Chi Square analysis for the difference in the overall academic performance between students in NCE Sandwich and NCE Regular Programme in Jigawa State college of Education.

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	26.237 ^a	10	.003
Likelihood Ratio	26.428	10	.003
Linear-by-Linear Association	19.843	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	1079		

Table 4 shows the chi square test of students from Part time NCE and Regular NCE programme in Jigawa state College of Education. The observed p-value is 0.003 which is less than 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis is hereby rejected because the observed p-value is less than the significant level p-value (0.05). Hence, there is significant difference on between the NCE Part time program and NCE Regular students.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students of Regular NCE and NCE Part time Programme in Jigawa state College of Education Gumel.

Table 5: Chi Square analysis for the difference between the academic performance of male and female students of Regular and NCE Part time program in Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	40.405 ^a	13	.025
Likelihood Ratio	41.885	13	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.728	1	.189
N of Valid Cases	1079		

Table 5 shows the chi square test for difference between the academic performance of male and female students of regular NCE and part time NCE programme in Jigawa state College of Education Gumel. The observed p-value is 0.025 which is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected because the observed p-value is less than the significant level p-value (0.05). Hence, there is significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students of regular NCE and part time NCE programme in Jigawa state College of Education Gumel.

Discussion of Findings

The result in research question one and hypotheses one in Tables 2 and 4 reveals that there is a significance difference in the performance of the regular NCE and part-time NCE students in terms of their performance, and that significant difference existed between the performance of regular students and part time students in favor of Regular NC students. Battle, J. & Michael, L. (2020) conducted research on factors influencing regular students' performance at university of Malaysia. The researchers found that four factors are positively related to students' performance viz-a-viz, demographic, active learning, students' attendance and involvement in extracurricular activities. However, course assessment was found to be negatively related to students' performance.

The result in research question two and hypotheses two in Tables 3 and 5 revealed that the performance of male and female students of regular NCE and part time NCE programme in Jigawa state College of Education Gumel. And that significant difference exists between the performance of male and female students of regular NCE and part time NCE programme. However, this result shows that the programme both part time and regular graduates is in favor of female students than male students. Ndlovu and Moyo (2013) conducted a study on the factors affecting performance of adults in adult and continuing education in Zimbabwe Open University. The results showed that the academic performance of the female study group performed better. However, the results indicated that male students' attitude toward learning affect academic performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

- i. The performance of regular NCE students is higher than the part-time NCE students in Jigawa State college of Education Gumel.
- ii. The female regular NCE students perform better than the male part time NCE students in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel.

Contributions to Knowledge

The results of this study provided the following contributions to knowledge:

- i. The study established that Regular NCE students perform better than the Part time NCE students in terms of their academic performance.
- ii. The study also established that their significance difference in gender, because female have higher mean academic performance than the male counterparts. Hence, there is need to give both males and females equal chance to learn and interact with instructional materials.

Recommendations from the Study

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:-

- i. It is recommended that extra-classes in the form of tutorials should be organized for the part-time classes so as to be able to meet up with the course content of the programme.
- ii. It is recommended that the male students in both the regular classes and the part-time classes should devote most of their time to their studies. So as to be able to complete favourably with their female counterparts.
- iii. The more experienced and most talented in the classes especially the part-time classes should be made to assist their class mates in those areas of study that they are weak at the teachers should also give them more tests and assignment to keep them busy during the week despite the fact that most of them have families and are civil servants or self-employed. They should be made to go through their work within the week before going for lectures on Fridays and Saturdays.
- iv. Male part-time students should learn how to plan their time as it predisposes them to become more organized and better planners, to weigh their priorities in order to meet deadlines. This is because effective time management will benefit both their studies and performance in school so that they will be able to compete with their female counterparts in the regular programme.

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